

Is a New Regional Order Emerging in the Middle East in the Aftermath of October 7?

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Through a combination of miscalculations, overreach, and unintended consequences, a new order is emerging in the Middle East in the wake of 7 October 2023. But it may not be the kind of order the United States and Israel hope to see. Instead, the maximalist agenda of the Israeli right, unreservedly embraced by the Trump administration, could stimulate a fragile Middle Eastern unity opposed to it and negate the benefits of neutralizing Iran's "Axis of Resistance."

Since 1979, and especially from 2003, the primary axis of conflict in the Middle East has been that between the US-backed Arab states and Israel, on the one hand, and Iran and its allies, on the other. Those Arab states that concluded peace treaties with Israel (Jordan and Egypt) actively assisted Israel in its occupation of Palestinian territory, while those that did not (the monarchies of the Gulf) quietly abetted it in deradicalizing the Palestinian resistance and containing its state sponsors. Iran, meanwhile, substantiated its revisionist status by cultivating clients in Lebanon, Syria, Palestine, Iraq, and Yemen, which correspondingly increased the sense of insecurity felt by other Arab regimes and helped them to claim American support.

Turkey's entry onto the regional stage from

the latter half of the 2000s complicated this bifurcated regional order, pitting an axis of "resistance" against an opposing one of "moderation". Central to the Turkish quest for regional influence was Ankara's endorsement of Hamas, the Muslim Brotherhood's Palestinian iteration, as a more democratically legitimate and efficacious representative of Palestinian aspirations than the supine Palestinian Authority. From 2011 Turkey also threw its weight behind the Brotherhood in Egypt and elsewhere. The Turkish model was in many ways more threatening to Saudi Arabia and Israel than the Iranian model as it offered a new formula for regional engagement with the West that would undermine US commitment to both Arab authoritarianism and maximalist Zionism. It also posed a greater challenge to Iran's model of Islamic resistance than did Israel or the Arab monarchies by dint of its greater potential to structurally penetrate Sunni Arab societies.

American disillusionment with Islamism in the context of the rise of ISIS, combined with Iranian and Saudi counter-revolutionary interventions (in Syria and Egypt, respectively), halted the rise of the Turkish model in the region. But the regional order did not simply return to the bifurcated antagonism that had prevailed pre-2011. Perceptions of American withdrawal from the Middle East sparked

a series of regional rapprochements. Under Chinese auspices, Saudi Arabia re-established diplomatic relations with the Islamic Republic and subsequently reconciled with the regime in Syria. Turkey was able to mend its relations with Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and Egypt—though notably not Assad. To complete the picture, Saudi Crown Prince Muhammad bin Salman openly confirmed that relations between the Kingdom and Israel were on the cusp of normalization (Spetalnick and Beech 2023).

It was in this context of growing regional rapprochement that Hamas launched its unprecedentedly lethal Al-Aqsa Flood operation on 7 October 2023. A response not only to the unremitting siege of Gaza but also to Arab-Israeli normalization at Palestine's expense, the attack precipitated a genocidal retaliation from Israel. It has succeeded in torpedoing the process of normalization between Saudi Arabia and Israel and brought Palestine back to the top of the diplomatic agenda. But if Hamas's intention was to tip the balance of power in the region toward the "Axis of Resistance", the strategy has been a resounding failure.

Israel's crushing response to the Hamas attack did indeed vivify the "Axis", prompting Hizbullah to open a northern front in solidarity with Palestine and forcing the first-ever direct Iranian military assault on Israel. But Hizbullah has paid a heavy price, and Iran's regional prestige and credibility have plummeted (Shami 2024). Although US allies Egypt, Jordan, and Turkey have also been exposed as, at best, incapable of restraining Israel and, at worst, complicit in its actions, Iran's abandonment of the Assad regime to its fate in November 2024 signaled Tehran's turn toward retrenchment. Its rapprochement with Saudi Arabia has notably held.

The blow to Iran's regional ambitions has removed a major incentive for Saudi Arabia to normalize with Israel anytime soon, particularly considering the severe reputational damage such a step would now invite. America's embrace of maximalist Zionism, unambiguously evidenced by Donald Trump's February 2025 proposal to "clean out" the Gaza Strip of its inhabitants and resettle them in Egypt and Jordan, has exposed the futility of signing peace treaties with Israel and generated powerful incentives for Arab and Turkish cooperation with Iran *against* the US and Israel. The "Turkish model", to the extent it still exists, no longer seriously threatens Saudi regional interests, and the Kingdom is closely involved with Ankara in the political transition in Syria. Iran will likely not abandon the resistance model altogether, but at the same time, it has few incentives to antagonize its neighbors.

Peace with Israel has, since the 1970s, been central to Middle Eastern state strategies to win economic, military, and political support from the United States to secure their regimes against internal threats. Complicity in a new Palestinian *nakba* would expose Western-allied regimes to unprecedented domestic pressure, and with Washington apparently nonchalant about this potential, the option of a more integrated regional order—of Arab states, Turkey, and Iran against Israel—may now represent the most appealing option. It will, however, be a negative and fragile unity based upon the absence of any attractive or viable alternatives. And whether a more integrated region, with all states except Iran still heavily dependent upon the West, will yield tangible benefits for Palestinians is very much an open question. The Palestine cause, with or without Hamas at its helm, is not going to disappear. A potential revival of Russian capacity in the region—particularly if it can

secure victory in the Ukraine conflict and in the context of the US potentially cutting aid to Egypt and Jordan (Kanno-Youngs and McCreesh 2025) or a more assertive Chinese regional role could easily resuscitate Iran's capacity to challenge Israeli, Saudi, and Turkish dominance and rearrange the pieces on the regional chessboard once more. ♦

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